

Opportunities of an Industrial City in the Leisure Tourism

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Abstract—The aim of the research is to investigate the forms of the demands of leisure tourism in a West-Hungarian industrial city, Győr. Today, Győr is still a traditional industrial city, its industry is mainly based on vehicle industry, but the role of tourism is increasing in the life of the city as well. Because of the industrial nature and the strong economy of the city, the ratio of business tourists is high. It can be stated that MICE tourism is dominating in Győr. Developments of the last decade can help the city with new tourism products to increase the leisure tourism. The new types of tourism – besides business tourism – can help the providers to increase the occupancy rates and the demand at the weekends. The research demonstrates the theoretical background of the topic, and it shows the present situation of the tourism in Győr with secondary data. The secondary research contains statistical data from the Hungarian Statistical Office and the city council, and it is based on the providers' data. The next part of the paper shows the potential types of leisure tourism with the help of primary research. The primary research contains the results of an online questionnaire with a sample of 1000 potential customers. It is completed with 10 in-depth interviews with tourism experts, who explained their opinions about the opportunities of leisure tourism in Győr from the providers' side. The online questionnaire was filled out in spring 2017 by customers, who have already stayed in Győr or plan to visit the city. At the same time in-depth interviews were made with hotel managers, head of touristic institutions and employees at the council. Based on the research it can be stated that the touristic supply of Győr allows the increase of the leisure tourism ratio in the city. Primarily, the cultural and health tourism show potential development, but the supply side of touristic services can be developed in order to increase the number of guest nights. The tourism marketing needs to be strengthened in the city, and a distinctive marketing activity - from other cities - is needed as well. To conclude, although Győr is an industrial city, it has a transforming industrial part, and tourism is also strongly present in its economy. Besides the leading role of business tourism, different types of leisure tourism have the opportunity to take place in the city.

Keywords—Business Tourism, Győr, industrial city, leisure tourism, touristic demand.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE study is about the city of Győr which is one of the most dynamically developing cities of Hungary. The geographical situation of the city is extremely favourable from the point of view of economy, transport and tourism too; it is situated in the middle of an imaginary triangle bordered by the capitals of three neighbouring countries, Hungary, Austria and Slovakia, just halfway between Budapest and Vienna. The

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distance between Győr and Budapest is 130 km, 122 km between Győr and Vienna and 80 km between Győr and Bratislava. These 4 cities are also connected by the river Danube. Győr has the river port by the city (Gönyű) and an airport (Pér) too. The number of the permanent population runs to 129 000 people, with which it is the 6th most populated city of Hungary but from the economic point of view it takes the 2nd place after Budapest [1].

Fig. 1 Location of Győr

Győr has a very rich historical past, it was a well-known settlement in the period of the Roman Empire too, under the name of „Arrabona”, later in the middle Ages, in 1271, it received city rank. It became a major city by the end of the 1800s, more than 300 grain traders were operating in the city in 1870, it also had a steam mill, agricultural machine factory, vinegar-oil and match factories. The real economic development started from the establishment of the wagon and machinery factory in 1896, later other heavy industry factories, textile plants, food product factories were also established, Győr has gradually developed into a significant industrial city [2].

After the end of the socialist regime, due to the changes in socio-economic circumstances, a great amount of factories were shut down. However, Győr has maintained its industrial character and significance, due to the arrival of new manufacturers. The most notable is the German car giant, Audi and its suppliers, following the establishment of the Audi manufacturing plant in 1993. Accordingly, the city cannot be characterized by the decline, relocation of industry but the development, thanks to continuous improvements and new investments.

The geographical location and rich historic past of the city create a favourable natural endowment and man-made environment for tourism. In Hungary, after Budapest and Sopron, the third most monuments and buildings of monument nature can be found in the city lying at the junction of three

rivers, in the historic downtown that is rich of built heritage.

Due to the industrial character of the city, business tourism has continued to be the most significant sector of tourism. However, leisure tourism has also been developing continuously as a result of growing cultural, educational and sports opportunities and facilities. "Since there's a race for customers on the market of the consumer goods, cities of the 21st century compete for the inhabitants, tourists, investors and international companies. In this competition a huge scale of city marketing tools are available, the image and good reputation of the city, their conscious framing are of the biggest feats of arms. The economy of the dynamically developing city, Győr experienced several system changes, it had transformed from a commercial city to an industrial one, and nowadays it has been transited to a dynamically developing centre." [3].

The city's leadership and the hospitality sector are constantly looking for the opportunities for the development of the leisure time tourism, because of the increase of its proportion, in order to make a firm stand.

Our research is looking into the possibilities and directions for the development of leisure tourism in Győr. The city keeps the characteristics of an "advanced, industrial city" but also shows an image of a dynamically developing, innovative and versatile city both for its residents and its visitors. The new slogan of Győr, which has been introduced in 2012, also strengthens this image: "Health, Culture, Innovation. The future is built in Győr!"

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature of tourism began to expand in the 1980s with books and publications, the topic of which is the city; in one focus of the researches is the peculiarities of urban tourism. Ashworth, Ashworth and Vogd investigated cities from a marketing approach, their salability and the opportunities how to increase their tourism [4], [5]. A significant part of the international literature deals with the features discovered during the research of major cities and metropolises, however, medium and small cities are relatively rarely at the centre of interest of researchers.

From the point of view of tourism, it is worth distinguishing cities based on their size and significance (capitals, cities, historic cities, small towns), which define the historical cityscape, attractions, city conference, stalls and other opportunities for tourists [6, p.15]. In relation to leisure tourism, it deals specifically with the significance of the city brakes, which is typical for the large cities with airport and major tourist attractions first of all. It devotes a separate chapter for the cultural, sports and special events, which can be the main motivation for most tourists when visiting a city, but it values the role of museums as tourist attractions in urban tourism. It also covers the structure of the expenditures of the urban tourists, according to which the tourists spend 35% on hotels, 24% on meals, 19% on shopping, entertainment and 8% on others. Interestingly, many surveys have shown similar expenditure rates and willingness since then, irrespective of

the year and the tourist destination, the difference lies in the cost of travel to the city [6, pp. 34-89].

In one of his studies, Paskaleva-Shapira supports the need to carry out an environmental analysis when analysing a particular city's tourism, identify the most important social, technological, economic, environmental and political impacts. The decisive dimensions of the competitiveness of urban tourism are: physical characteristics of the city, urban community elements, management (supply oriented), marketing (visitor oriented) [7].

Spiroou classifies the districts of tourism in the city into different types, (types of tourism districts) and proposes development opportunities accordingly and evaluates the impact of mega sports events on urban development [8].

In several articles, Richards deals with the importance of creativity in urban tourism. Earlier in 2011, he examined the effects of the cultural events in his book with his co-author through the example of Rotterdam as European Capital of Culture [9], [10].

In urban tourism, the number, quality, attractiveness, and the impact on guests and guest nights are decisive. According to Richards, creativity has a major role in developing new tourism products, in the revitalisation of existing products, creation of the atmosphere of the cities, specific venues and in city branding [11].

Valls et al. studied the tourism of the most important cities of Europe. It was found that the features of city tourism, short breaks, long holidays are different in international and domestic tourism. Paris, London and Rome have a leading role in Europe, but in domestic tourism, Hamburg, Florence and Berlin are leading the list. They have evaluated and sought relationships between the attitudes of cities and those of tourists choosing cities, as well as the marketing communications that can be used by cities [12].

In another study, Cibinskienea and Snieskieneb state that the competitiveness of urban tourism is also influenced by factors such as the external and internal environment, tourism resources, and infrastructural features [13].

Tokarchuk et al. researched the relationship between the development of the city tourism products and the well-being of the city residents of the illustrative German cities. It has been shown that many tourism developments have a positive impact on community, which is also beneficial to the local residents and has a good impact on quality of life [14].

Mikulić et al. examined the relationship between the brand strengths of the European capitals and the tourism intensity. In their analysis they have shown the strong, significant relationship between them. The Saffron European City Brand Barometer used by them applies four subjective factors, Quantity/strength of positive/attractive associations (weight: 25%), pictorially recognized (weight: 25%), Conversational value (weight: 25%), Media recognition (weight: 25%) when determining the brand strength of a city. The method can be used to explore the relationship with tourism intensity containing objective data [15].

The Hungarian scientific and tourism literature deals with the analysis of the most important cities, some of these studies

have analysed tourism in Győr. Michalkó elaborated in detail the urban development aspects of tourism in his book. According to Michalkó, cities are recreational spaces, where tourists visit sights and they make use of tourist services. In a market-oriented approach, the city is a recreational product used by tourists to gain experience [16]. Tóth deals with the city's tourism, hotel industry, hotel features, accommodation structure in the city, the supply and demand of hotels, the competitiveness of the Hungarian tourist destinations [17]. According to Tóthné's research, the industrial city of Győr is undergoing transformation, more and more emphasis is placed on tourism, which is also perceived by the permanent population of the city. Infrastructural, institutional developments of the recent years (visitor centre, hotels) and the cultural events which are organized not only for the city population already, and the tourism attraction programs draw a significant number of tourists to the city which can also be detected in the growth of tourism revenues [18].

In his book, „Territorial capital in urban development – The code Győr” [19], Rechnitzer deals with tourism in several places. He considers the growing shopping tourism that came up in the cities in the 1960s and 1970s as an important factor in innovation which grew stronger after the political transformation and had a trade-rearing effect. Most of the city's hotels served a steadily growing economy, investments of the emerging new businesses, from the 90s a major business tourism was developed. There was a growing demand for higher-category hotels, while the demand for guest-houses and simpler hotels declined [19].

III. CHARACTERISTICS OF TOURISM IN GYŐR

The tourism of Győr is based on MICE tourism, within which the travels of businessmen arriving to the companies and institutions in Győr are dominant; the guest nights spent on accommodations are also linked to them. The industrial park which was originally opened in 1992 and had 126 hectares then has to be expanded several times due to the high number of settling companies. The factories in the industrial park, such as the world's largest motorcycle factory in Győr, Audi's many contracted suppliers and other independent factories have boosted industrial production and tourism in the city again.

Over the last decades it has also been observed that investment in the city's businesses and the construction of shopping centres generates the larger part of business tourism. When no major corporate investment is underway, stagnation is typical and this is very much perceived by hotels, restaurants, tourist service providers and due to the missed traffic and tax incomes the city itself is also affected. Tourism is so much affected by this investment addiction in the city that it has long been argued that dependence should be reduced by developing tourism supply, increasing the rate and share of leisure tourism.

Conference tourism also plays a significant role in the tourism of the city, thanks to Petz Aladár County Training Hospital. In addition, national and regional companies often hold economic, technical training, re-trainings, conferences in

the city too. However, the city does not have a real conference centre, the building of Győr-Moson-Sopron County Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Széchenyi István University, the National Theater of Győr and private rooms of the hotels are suitable for the execution of conferences and events of these types first of all.

Cultural tourism is the tourist product of Győr that can be classified into the recreational category. Győr is not only an industrial but a cultural city too, with excellent features which really entitles the city that more and more tourists explore this side of it too. The town is home to the world-famous Ballet of Győr, whose founder was Iván Markó who was the solo dancer of the Maurice Béjart Company once. Győr has become a festival town for the past two decades, throughout the year art, music, dance, and other festivals are constantly on the line. The city's tourism development strategy in 2007 has still considered the role of previous festivals so that events outside the region cannot attract tourists to the city [20]. Fortunately, the situation has changed; many regular festivals have been able to gain a national reputation which also affects guest nights in the city. One of these events is the "Győrköc" festival which is a pun that refers to the city of Győr and the children as well. For a summer weekend children obtain the downtown of Győr with lots of programs, shows and quiz-games. Of course, children are accompanied by their parents, at that time all hotels in the city are full of domestic guests from all over the country.

Due to its diverse and extremely rich cultural life, its excellent institutions, Győr is applying for the title of the European Capital of Culture 2023, and it is certain that, if the title is awarded, it will be able to run a unique high-quality program series [21].

Religious tourism in the city is becoming more and more important, thanks to the important souvenirs in the basilica of the city, to the liturgy of Saint László, the tearful Virgin Mary image of Ireland and the happy Apor Vilmos tomb. Events associated with them attract thousands of pilgrims every year. Not far from Győr, about 23 km away, you can find Pannonhalma, of which Benedictine Monastery is on the UNESCO World Heritage List. The proximity of the two cities reinforces the potential touristic attraction of both cities, not only for those who travels with religious purposes.

The sporting life of the city is prominent on a national level, but it also had a number of international sports events. Győr is one of the strongholds of handball in the world, the three-time BL winner women's handball team of the Audi ETO KC is operating in the city. In recent years, the best women's handball players have already visited the city either as the member of the team of Győr or as a player of another team. Thanks to the rivers' opportunities, the Marathon Kayak Canoe World Championship has been organized several times in the city. In the summer of 2017 the European Youth Olympic Festival (EYOF) has been organized by the city as well. Due to the large sports event, new sports facilities, accommodation were built, the older ones were refurbished and the quality and capacity of the city's sports infrastructure has increased.

Interestingly, the city has a hotel, stadium, shopping building complex (ETO Sport and Leisure Park), where hotel guests can book rooms with windows overlooking the football stadium, from where they can watch events taking place in the stadium without admission.

Rába Quelle Spa, Thermal and Adventure Bath was established in 2004. It is built upon thermal water which is suitable for healing of locomotion disorders. The spa and adventure bath receive about half a million guests a year, two thirds of them are Hungarian, one third are foreign, mainly Slovak, Czech and Austrian tourists. Rába Quelle Spa, Thermal and Adventure Bath could provide an excellent place for a spa or wellness hotel with high quality and big capacity. In the mid-eighties, plans were made for such a hotel at the thermal bath, but unfortunately, neither of these nor any other future spa or wellness hotel investments has been realized since then. The spa or wellness hotel could represent the appearance of new guests in the city as it is today and could increase the stay time and earning as well. According to the experience of the Hungarian spa and wellness hotels, the guests require a medical centre, treatment rooms, wellness area and pools at the hotel. Spa and wellness guests are less likely to choose hotels where these departments are not on the spot, and the guests can only be taken from the hotel to the bath by transfer. Unfortunately in Győr there is an example for this and this hinders health tourism from becoming more popular in the city. However, one form of health tourism, dental tourism, has become very significant in the city, some hotels and dental clinics have specialized in attending foreign guests who arrive for dental treatments [22].

"City-break" multi-day tourism, which is typical of large cities, is still limited in the city. Thanks to the unified city tour packages offered by the city and the hotels, first of all domestic tourists arrive on weekends and on holidays mainly. Different packages are for different target groups, depending on the built-in services and program options. There is a package offer which contains a spa entry ticket, theatre or concert ticket, zoo ticket, sightseeing tour with a guide or horse carriage ride, boat ride on the rivers of the city, etc.

Shopping tourism, due to the proximity of the Austrian and Slovak borders and the high-quality shopping malls in Győr, is also typical for the weekend, but with strong fluctuations, mainly due to fluctuations in the exchange rate of the euro/Hungarian forint.

Active tourism is also present in the city during the summer high season. Győr, as part of the Eurovelo 6 European Bicycle Route network, offers a one-night stay to the foreign tourists cycling from Vienna to Budapest. Unfortunately, the possibilities of water tourism are not developed and exploited well in the city. Szigetköz which is suitable for this purpose is very close, one part of Győr already belongs to Szigetköz and the river sections of the city could be used as a starting or arriving station for canoe tours. As a result of the economic crisis, the number of guests and guest nights in Győr dropped slightly in 2009 compared to the previous year, but it started to grow significantly from the following year (Fig. 2). The effect of the construction of a new plant in the Audi factory in 2012

meant a record in the tourism industry in Győr and after a prominent year, there was a slight downturn but the developments continued afterwards. In addition to Audi, other plants have also invested, so the results of the guest's turnover in 2016 surpassed even the previous four years. The hotels in Győr meet the requirements of MICE tourism first of all, within this the individual business travellers are the strongest segment, they are mainly the employees or business partners of Audi and the supplying companies. Hotel services are also tailored to the needs of individual business travellers first of all, while the guests who stay longer and require a range of high-quality leisure and entertainment services within hotels are less typical. The average tourist now stays in Hungary for only three days, well below the European average. [23]. The average length of a stay in Győr is 2.2 guest nights/person which is below the national average of 2.5 guest nights/person each year [1].

Fig. 2 Guest and Guest nights in Győr between 2008 and 2016 (Thousand) [1]

According to a previous research, the number of hotel guest nights that can be linked directly to a cultural festival or event in Győr is about 2-3% compared to all guest nights [24]. Since then, there have been many more festivals and cultural events in the city that generate hotel and accommodation stay, but also the size of business tourism in the city has increased, so the rates have only slightly changed.

Fig. 3 Domestic and International Guest nights in Győr between 2008 and 2016 (Thousand) [1]

Domestic tourism has also started to grow in Győr (Fig. 3) which, similar to the national trends, is the consequence of the incentive effect of the Széchenyi Recreation Card that is exercised on the domestic tourism. More and more domestic guests visit the city, use the previously mentioned sightseeing packages and cultural events and festivals also have an increasing effect on the number of domestic guests and guest

nights.

Business tourism has exercised a beneficial effect on the growth of the number of domestic guest nights of the last three years too. Foreign-owned companies also used many Hungarian subcontractors for their investments and for the successful implementation of the projects. Hungarian specialists had to be accommodated in one of the hotels in Győr too.

The capacities of the hotels in Győr have changed over the past decade (Fig. 4); four major new hotels have entered the hotel market in Győr; Famulus, Ibis, the WHB in the International Industrial Park, and the "Stadium Review" ETO Park Hotel. These hotels made a significant contribution to the accommodation of the guests arriving in the city for the execution of investments in the city.

Fig. 4 Changes of accommodation capacities in Győr between 2008 and 2016 (Thousand) [1]

Formerly a large hotel (Danubius Hotel Rába City Center) and a few smaller 25-30 rooms represented high quality accommodation and hospitality in Győr but due to the continuous development of the city and tourism there were periods when their total capacity was exceeded. It often happened that beside the accommodation of the regular business guests there was no capacity for the guests of larger events, conferences or sport events and for leisure guests as well. Accommodation developments have followed the development of the city at a good pace and the opportunities for growing tourism have also been created.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The city has a very strong industry, based mainly on vehicle industry. The aim of the research is to map the new opportunities and collect the parts of the supply side in leisure tourism. The main form of the tourism in Győr is business tourism, but there are a lot of opportunities to develop other types of tourism in the city. The primary research focuses on the motivation of potential tourists and the tourists who have already visited the city. It investigated which services they usually take during their stay in the city. The research also examined the source of information used by the tourist about the city and the services it offers. Based on the research objectives the following research question was drawn.

RQ: What types of leisure tourism have potential demand beside business tourism among potential leisure tourists in Győr?

The database of the research was built from three sources.

The secondary research contains statistical data from the Hungarian Central Statistical Office and the city council, and it is based on the providers' data. The primary research contains the results of an online questionnaire with a sample of 1055 potential customers. The primary research was completed with in-depth interviews. 10 experts from the tourism sector were asked about their opinion on how to increase leisure tourism in Győr.

In accordance with the previously proposed objectives, a questionnaire has been developed for tourists who are interested in visiting Győr in order to obtain the information. The online questionnaire was filled out between 05.03 and 11.04.2017 by customers who have already stayed in Győr or are planning to visit the city. 217 surveys were cancelled from the 1272 surveys either because the participant lives in Győr or the respondents do not want visit the city. A total of 1055 valid surveys were examined. We used the SPSS statistical program (version 15.0 for Windows) to analyse the results. The in-depth interviews were made in spring of 2017 with hotel managers, head of touristic institutions and employees at the council.

V. RESULTS

In this study, descriptive statistics were used to display demographic information.

TABLE I
 DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION		
Gender	Male	32%
	Female	68%
Age	15-19	6%
	20-29	41%
	30-39	16%
	40-49	15%
	50-59	15%
	60+	6%
Marital status	Single	26%
	Married	67%
	Divorced	4%
	Widowed	3%
Education	Primary school	4%
	Vocational training	11%
	High school graduate	43%
	Professional degree	14%
	Bachelor's/Master's degree	28%

Most of the respondents (80%) have already stayed in Győr and 20% of them are planning to visit the city. We analysed the demographic information with this dimension as well. The analysis shows a significant difference at the age dimension. Respondents in the age group of 20-29 are over-represented in the group of „already stayed in Győr”. The division of age is more consistent in the group of „plan to visit the city”. In point of gender and education, the two groups show analogy. Overall, it could be verified that the two groups of respondents can be used for comparison of motivation/action/attitude variables.

After obtaining the data, we proceeded to analyse the

reliability of the scales. A procedure for measuring the reliability is determination of its internal consistency. The Cronbach's Alpha (α) estimates the internal consistency of a measurement scale. [25] The coefficient usually varies between 0 and 1, although it can take negative values when there are items that are negatively correlated. A coefficient value between 0.7-0.6 usually indicates a questionable internal consistency. In the whole sample $\alpha=0.638$, and in the other groups $\alpha=0.628$ and 0.668 . With this value, the overall consistency of the dependent variables will be acceptable.

A. Motivation of the Visit

For the motivation of the visit, respondents could indicate several responses. The multiple-choice questions were converted element by element to a dichotomous. Fig. 5 shows the distribution of the whole sample for all motivations. According to the respondents and based on the analysis, it can be stated that cultural programs and sightseeing are the most attractive programs in Győr. The average number of selected motivations was 2.59 per respondent, most respondents indicated 2 (27.7%) or 3 (24.7%) motivations in the questionnaire.

Fig. 5 Motivations of the visit

After analysing the correlation of the different motivations, Tab II shows the following results. In the table, the different colours show significant covariance (lighter: $p = 95\%$, darker: $p = 99\%$).

TABLE II
CORRELATION OF THE DIFFERENT MOTIVATIONS

	VFR tourism	cultural programs	sightseeing	sport events	religious tourism	shopping	health tourism	entertainment
cultural programs	0,074							
sightseeing	0,016	0,110						
sport events	0,040	0,084	-0,002					
religious tourism	0,045	0,041	0,049	-0,010				
shopping	0,158	0,136	-0,050	0,139	-0,085			
health tourism	0,020	0,113	0,020	0,081	0,070	0,143		
entertainment	0,044	0,025	0,044	0,064	-0,103	0,117	0,176	
MICE tourism	0,082	0,062	0,034	0,040	0,022	0,070	0,056	0,052

Correlation is the association between changes in the values of two variables. The linear correlation coefficient is a measure of the degree of direction between two variables. It can take values between -1 and 1. A value of 0 indicates no correlation. If the coefficient is positive, it expresses a covariance of variables in the same direction, and a negative coefficient, the opposite. The correlation coefficients between a set of variables can be presented as a correlation matrix, which is a double-entry table showing the correlation coefficients between all possible pairs of the variables considered in the analysis. It is also evident from the table that the most popular purpose of visit is cultural program and a significant part of other activities (sightseeing, sport, shopping, health, business) are grouped around it. Shopping as the goal of a visit appears as a "supplementary" program for most purposes. Negative significance can only be seen in the case of religious tourism as the motivation of religious tourism is not related to shopping and entertainment purposes. Sightseeing is the most "neutral" motivation; apart from cultural programs, it is not really related to anything.

Having analysed the two groups of respondents (have already stayed in Győr – plan to visit), the following differences have been found in their motivations (Fig. 6).

There are also significant differences in four of the motivations. Shopping, entertainment and visiting sport events are the motivations where the mention rate of respondents, who have already stayed in Győr, is higher. The religious purpose is the only motivation where respondents, who only plan to visit the city, have a higher ratio. (The sightseeing shows the same difference, but the difference here is not significant).

The motivation of tourists can also be examined in socio-demographic variables. The whole sample shows relatively more significant relationships; especially the age of the participants significantly influences the choice of specific goal(s). Visiting friends and relatives, sports events, shopping and entertainment can be considered as the choice of the younger generation, while religious tourism is more common in the older age group.

The study of the two sub-samples – have already stayed in Győr and plan to visit – shows that the planning of the visit is tied relatively less to the socio-demographic characteristics. On the other hand, the realised visit has linear correlation with the variables.

In the matrix (Table III), the links and their type are illustrated with colours (white - no correlation, grey –

correlation, but not linear, or linearity cannot be interpreted, correlation).
 black - negative linear correlation, squared - positive linear correlation).

	shopping	cultural programs	entertainment	sightseeing	VFR tourism	sport events	health tourism	MICE tourism	religious tourism
plan to visit	29,9	49,5	41,6	54,7	37,4	14,5	13,1	5,1	13,1
have already stayed in Győr	55,1	55,1	49,5	48,5	44	23,2	16,8	7,8	5,6

Fig. 6 Motivations of the sub-samples

TABLE III
 CORRELATION OF THE DIFFERENT MOTIVATIONS AND SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES IN THE TWO SUB-SAMPLES

B. Information's Sources

The research also investigated the source of information for tourists about the city and its services. Fig. 7 shows the distribution of the whole sample.

Fig. 7 Information's sources

When planning the marketing communication activities, the Internet as a communication channel should also be a must for the city marketing. The recommendation of services by acquaintances is another important personal source.

Based on the study of the two sub-samples, internet sources and recommendation show significant difference. Respondents, who have already stayed in Győr, mentioned these communication tools in higher numbers. Printed publications (leaflets) show significant correlation as well, but in a reverse direction.

Based on the analysis of socio-demographic correlations, age is the strongest determinant in choosing information sources. The internet is rather used by young people, while other mass media (printed media, TV, radio) are used by older people.

Studying the two sub-samples, it is basically the same as with the previous questions; fewer connections can be found in the group of respondents, who only plan to travel to the city.

TABLE IV
 CORRELATION OF INFORMATION'S SOURCES AND SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES IN THE TWO SUB-SAMPLES

	Have already stayed in Győr				Plan to visit			
	Gender	Age	Marital status	Education	Gender	Age	Marital status	Education
Recommendation								
Printed media								
Information points								
Printed publication								
Internet								
TV, radio								
Exhibition, fairs								

The research also examined what websites or platforms are used to find information about the city and its services. Around 70% of the respondents use social media sites, but the websites of the providers and the official website of the city are also frequently used for getting more information.

TABLE V
 CORRELATION OF WEBSITES AND SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

	Gender	Age	Marital status	Education
Official website of the city				
social media sites				
website of the providers				
booking.com				
szallas.hu				
tripadvisor.com				

The research shows that age is the most powerful factor in this matter. Older people are more conservative, and they tend to look at the official website or booking sites in Hungarian language, while younger people usually use social media sites. Other socio-demographic factors do not show any linear correlation.

C. Use of Accommodation

The next question investigates whether the respondents would have an accommodation and the following results were found. Based on the secondary research, Győr has an average stay of 2.1 nights. Fig. 8 shows clearly that there is a significant difference between the two sub-samples (already stayed in Győr and plan to visit the city).

Fig. 8 Use of accommodation

Based on the primary research, there is a difference between

the two sub-samples. It is also apparent that those who only plan the trip would spend longer time in the city, than those who have already been to Győr. The socio-demographic factors show many significant differences in this respect, but these correlations mostly have no linearity/hierarchy.

D. Lack of Services

There is a lot of interesting data in the answers with respect to how to extend the time spent in the city. These are also related to motivations and also show what services are needed in the city.

Fig. 9 Lack of services

The research shows that mostly, general leisure time activities like events and entertainment opportunities were mentioned, but the wellness hotel was also very attractive, because the city did not have any wellness hotels at the time.

In the case of the two sub-samples, the significant differences appear in the case of sport events. In both cases, better accommodation was mentioned by a higher amount of respondents from the group those who are only planning a visit.

VI. CONCLUSION

The basic objective of the present study was to analyse the possibilities of different types of leisure tourism in Győr. The secondary research showed that the tourism of the city is built on the business tourism, but there are a lot of opportunities on the supply side as well.

The research question of the study was what types of leisure tourism have potential demand in Győr. From the results obtained, it can be observed that cultural tourism shows potential development and other types of leisure tourism

(sightseeing, shopping, etc.) are connected with it. Health tourism can also be developed in order to increase the number of guest-nights. To attract more tourists in this type of tourism, the city has to develop the supply side of touristic services (e.g. wellness hotel, more services in the spa).

The result of the research shows that the marketing activities in Győr should be improved and its marketing communication needs a distinctive message to be unique on the market. The study shows that social media sites and websites of the providers and the official website of the city are the most important communication channels in the marketing activity.

Based on the research it can be stated that the touristic supply of Győr allows the increase of leisure tourism ratio in the city.

To conclude, the results of the research show that beside industry, tourism has an important role in the life of the city as well. Business tourism has a high market share in Győr, but potential tourists from various target groups also have needs in leisure tourism.

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